

**TOSHKENT VILOYATI SHAROITIDA SOYA DALASIDAGI
ZARPECHAKKA QARSHI ZETA 100 G/L GERBITSIDINI
QO‘LLASHNING SAMARADORLIGI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada soya, kungaboqar dalalarida, dala chetlari, ariq va kanal bo‘ylaridagi zarpechaklarni yo‘qotishda ularni tarqalishini oldini oluvchi, agrotexnik hamda kimyoviy kurash choralarining samarali usullari ishlab chiqish iborat.

Kalit so‘zlar: Qarshi kurash, soya, kungaboqar, gerbitsid, pilot, zeta, yerga ishlov berish, agrotexnologiya, hosildorlik, samaradorlik.

ABSTRACT:

This article consists in the development of effective methods of agrotechnical and chemical struggle measures that prevent them from spreading in the fields of soybeans, sunflowers, in the loss of Goldsmiths on the edges of fields, ditches and Channel necks.

Key words: Fight against, soybean, sunflower, herbicide, pilot, Zeta, ground processing, Agrotechnology, productivity, efficiency.

KIRISH: Aholiga arzon va sifatli qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlari yetkazib berish, mahsulotlarning fitosanitar holatini yaxshilash, karantin ostidagi ob‘ektlarni respublikaga kirib kelishini oldini olish maqsadida O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017 yil 30 avgustdagi «O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi O‘simliklar karantini davlat inspeksiyasini tashkil etish to‘g‘risida» PF-5174-sonli farmoni hamda 2018 yil 28 martdagi «O‘simliklarni karantini bo‘yicha davlat xizmati faoliyatining samaradorligini oshirishga doir

qo‘shimcha chora-tadbirlar to‘g‘risida» gi PQ-3626-sonli qarori qabul qilindi.

Ushbu farmon va qarorlar ijrosini ta‘minlashda, moyli ekinlarning karantin kasalliklari va zarpechak begona o‘tiga qarshi samarali tejamkor kurash tizimini ishlab chiqish hamda o‘simliklarni fitosanitar xolatini yaxshilash, ilmiy asoslangan davlat nazorati tizimini yanada takomillashtirish ushbu loyihaning oldiga qo‘yilgan muhim vazifasi hisoblanadi.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METODOLOGIYASI: Hozirgi zarpechak turlari janubiy mintaqada, yog‘ingarchilik me‘yorida bo‘lgan hududlarda yaxshi rivojlanadi. Shuning uchun shimolga tomon ularning tarqalishi kamayib boradi. Ayrim turlar faqat bir joyga moslashgan, masalan *C.engelmanii Korsh.* faqat Markaziy Osiyoda uchraydi [1. S. 94]). Zarpechakni qishloq xo‘jalik ekinlarida tarqalgan turlarining biologiyasi va keltiradigan zarari bo‘yicha [2. 11-13], [2. r. 94-95], [2. 12 [kabi olimlar ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borishgan.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI.

Zeta gerbitsidining turli me‘yorda qo‘llashning Soya dalasidagi zarpechakka qarshi ta‘siri Toshkent Davlat agrar universitetining tajriba stansiyasida 6 ta variant, 4 ta takrorlashda. Har bir variant bo‘lagi 84 m² qilib olindi. Maydonchalarga soya ekilishi bilan birga tuproq yuzasiga 3-4 sm chuqurlikka zarpechak urug‘lari (400 dona) ham ekildi. Zellek-super, 104 g/l e.k. 1,0 l/ga etalon sifatida olindi. Zeta gerbitsidi 0,5; 0,8; 1,0 1,2 l/ga me‘yorlarda soyaning birinchi sug‘orishidan keyin qo‘lda sepgich apparat bilan bir tekis sepildi. Har bir sarf me‘yordagi ishchi eritmasidan 300 l/ga suv hisobidan sarflangan.

Daladagi boshqa agrotexnik tadbirlar soya yetishtirish uchun joriy etilgan texnologik jarayonlar asosida amalga oshirildi.

Olingan ma‘lumotlardan ko‘rinib turibdiki, 5 iyunda tajriba dalasida zarpechakning tarqalishi 14,6-16,0 % bo‘lgan (3.5.1-jadval).

Birinchi hisob gerbitsidlar sepilgandan keyin 15 kun o‘tib olindi. Zellek-super sepilgan variantda soya o‘simligining zarpechak bilan zararlanishi 15,5 % ni tashkil etgan. Bu dastlabki davrga nisbatan 0,9 % ko‘paygan. Lekin nazorat variantiga nisbatan 26,9 % kam bo‘lgan.

Zeta gerbitsidi 0,5 l/ga me‘yorda sepilgan variantda gerbitsid sepish davrida 15,7 % soya o‘simligi zarpechak bilan zararlangan. Birinchi hisob davrida zarpechak bilan zararlanish 3,5 % tashkil etib samaradorlik 77,7 % ga teng bo‘lgan. Nazorat variantiga nisbatan esa 83,5 % bo‘lgan. Zeta, 100 g/l gerbitsidi 0,8 l/ga me‘yorda qo‘llanilgan variantda gerbitsidni sepishdan oldin soya o‘simligi 16 % zarpechak bilan zararlangan. O‘n besh kundan keyin olingan birinchi hisob davrida zarpechak bilan zararlangan o‘simliklar soni 1,5 % ni tashkil etgan. Samaradorlik 90 % ga teng bo‘lgan. Nazorat

variantiga nisbatan zararlanish 19,7 % kam kam bo'lgan. Gerbitsidning samaradorligi 92,9 % ni tashkil etgan.

Zeta, 100 g/l gerbitsidi 1,0 l/ga me'yorda ishlatilgan variantda gerbitsid sepishdan oldin zarpechak bilan zararlangan soya o'simligi soni 15,8 % ga teng bo'lgan. Gerbitsid sepilgandan 15 kundan keyin zararlangan o'simliklar soni 1,0 % ni tashkil etdi. Bu variantda samaradorlik 93,7 % ga teng bo'lgan. Gerbitsid sepilmagan nazorat variantiga nisbatan samaradorlik 96,2 % ni tashkil etgan.

Zeta, 100 g/l gerbitsidi 1,2 l/ga me'yorda qo'llanilgan variantda gerbitsid sepish paytida zarpechak bilan zararlangan soya o'simligi soni 15,0 % ga teng bo'lgan. Preparat sepilgandan 15 kundan keyin zararlangan o'simliklar soni 0,8 % ni tashkil etdi. Bu variantda samaradorlik 94,7 % ga teng bo'lgan. Gerbitsid sepilmagan nazorat variantiga nisbatan samaradorlik 95,3 % ni tashkil etgan.

Gerbitsidlar sepilgandan keyin 30 kun o'tib olingan ikkinchi hisob davrida zarpechak bilan zararlangan o'simliklarning soni hamma variantlarda ko'paygan. Nazorat variantida soya o'simligining 45 % zarpechak bilan zararlandi. Zeta, 100 g/l 0,8 l/ga me'yorda sepilgan variantda zararlanish 2,7 % ga teng bo'lgan. Bu gerbitsid 1,0 l/ga me'yorda qo'llanilgan variantda bu ko'rsatkich 1,5 %, 1,2 l/ga me'yorda qo'llanilganda 1,0 % ga teng bo'ldi.

Zeta, 100 g/l 0,8 l/ga me'yorda sepilgan variantda soya o'simligining zarpechak bilan zararlanishi hosilni yig'ib olish davrida 4,5 % ga teng bo'lgan. Bu variantda dastlabki zararlanishga nisbatan samaradorlik 75,0 % ni tashkil etdi. Samaradorlik nazorat variantiga nisbatan 93,6 % ni tashkil etgan.

Zeta, 100 g/l 1,0 l/ga me'yorda sepilgan variantda zararlanish hosilni yig'ib olish davrida 2,5 % ga teng bo'lgan. Bu variantda dastlabki zararlanishga nisbatan samaradorlik 84,2 % ni tashkil etdi. Samaradorlik nazorat variantiga nisbatan 96,6 % ni tashkil etgan.

Zeta, 100 g/l 1,2 l/ga me'yorda sepilgan variantda zararlanish hosilni yig'ib olish davrida 1,7 % ga teng bo'ldi. Samaradorlik bu variantda nazorat nisbatan 97,6 % ni tashkil qildi. Bu preparat 1,5 l/ga me'yorda ishlatilgan variantda soya hosilini yig'ib olish paytida zarpechakning tarqalishi 3,2 % ni tashkil etgan.

XULOSA: Zeta gerbitsidi 0,5 va 0,8 me'yorlarda qo'llanilgan variantlarida soyadan mos ravishda 26,4 va 28,0 s/ga hosil olingan. Bu gerbitsid nisbatan yuqori me'yorlarda ishlatilganda 30,6 va 29,2 s/ga hosil olingan. Gerbitsid sepilmagan nazorat variantidan 22,7 s/ga hosil olingan.

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